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EMPOWERING TEACHERS TO CLIMATE ACTION

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Climate change (global warming) is the most urgent one of the wicked problems we face today. Europe has taken a strong stand in line with the Paris Agreement to limit global warming "well below 2 °C, and pursue efforts to keep it to to 1,5 °C". As we only have a few of decades to make radical changes to how much emissions we pollute to the atmosphere, every action for the benefit of the climate is important.

Students and young people in general are especially worried about the future of the planet and humankind. Engineering students are interested and willing to contribute to the subject with their professional competence, but tend to feel they do not get enough tools from education to channel their skills, competences and know-how in stopping climate change. This needs an urgent fix. To ensure that students get the skills and competences they aspire, the teachers need to improve their own understanding of climate change and how it relates to the subject at hand that they teach.

The workshop is aimed for

- Teachers interested in implementing climate change themes to their teaching,
- Teaching support personnel that wish to inspire teachers in their university to implementing climate solutions in their teaching, and
- Everyone interested in discussing and learning about implemeting climate solutions to engineering education

The workshop will start off with a short introduction to how different fields of technology contribute to causing and solving the climate crisis. After the introduction participants make their own plans for integrating climate solution themes in their own university curriculum or courses that they teach.

The participants will be provided with a canvas for planning their courses involving climate change themes. We will provide differentiated canvases for different fields of science and a general canvas for a more holistic approach. The participants from same fields of science are encouraged to collaborate on their planning to share their ideas and the facilitators of the workshop will provide constant support for the participants. As the end result of the workshop, all participants get to take their canvas plans home for further planning and implementation.